

Preferential Location of TiO₂ Particles in PET/PP Blend

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SUMMARY

Two types of TiO₂ nanoparticles (300nm and 15nm) are incorporated into PET/PP blend with or without PP-g-MA by using four different blending procedures. The effects of PP-g-MA and blending sequence on the location of TiO₂ were investigated. The phase morphology of the composites was also studied.

Keywords: composites; compatibilized; morphology; interfacial tension

INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, considerable research attention has been focused on introducing nanoscale fillers into polymer blends. It was found that the nanofillers always have a preferential location either in one polymer phase or at the interface, which exerts some compatibilization effect on the polymer blends. In polymer blends, the nanofillers are observed to be located either in one phase or at the interface. Some researchers argued that when located at the interface the nanofillers (especially the nanoclays) act as a physical barrier, which slows down the coalescence of the dispersed phases [1-3]. Other researchers reported that the nanofillers at the interface stabilize the blend morphology by reducing the interfacial tension [4-6]. However, if the nanofillers are preferentially located in one phase (usually in the matrix) the viscosity ratio between the matrix and dispersed phase is changed, which can significantly affect the phase morphology. Hong reported that in the PBT (polybutylene terephthalate)/PE (polyethylene) blend most of the nanoclays are located in the dispersed PBT phase when their concentration is high [7]. Therefore the deformability of the PBT droplets filled with organoclays is significantly reduced. The less likelihood of breakup of the droplet somewhat hinders the effect of the organoclays in the size reduction. So, an increase in the mean droplet size of PBT is observed at high nanoclay loading.

Many researchers have investigated the preferential location of the nanofillers in the polymer blends. Most of them attributed this phenomenon to a strong chemical affinity between the nanofillers and the corresponding polymer. As the nanofillers are usually surface modified, they tend to be “chemically bonded” to a given polymer [8-14]. However, some other researchers offered different explanations. For polymer blends filled with carbon black, the interfacial tension is the key factor determining the location of carbon black [15-18]. Elias investigated the PP/PS (polystyrene) blend filled with hydrophilic and hydrophobic nanosilica. The cited author attributed the preferential location of silica (hydrophilic silica in PS phase and hydrophobic silica in PP phase) to the lower interfacial tension between the nanoparticles and the preferred polymers [19].

Wu reported that the preferential location of nanofillers in two chemically different polymer melts is not always determined by the surface tension of polymers. In many cases, it is governed by the flexibility of polymer chains, which suggests that the entropy penalty may play a main role in competitive adsorption of polymers on the surfaces of nanofillers [20]. Lee studied the SiO₂/LCP (liquid crystal polymer)/PP ternary composites, and argued that the preferential location of the hydrophilic silica in the LCP phase is due to the polar interaction between them [21].

In the present work, TiO₂ particles (300 nm in diameter) were incorporated into PET/PP (minor/major) blends with or without PP-g-MA by using four different blending procedures. The effects of PP-g-MA and blending sequence on the location and migration of TiO₂ were investigated.

EXPERIMENT

Materials

The PET (skyPET BL8050) was provided by SK Eurochem (Warszawa, Poland) with the intrinsic viscosity of 0.80 dl/g. The PP (Novolen) was purchased from LyondellBasell (Netherlands) with a melt flow rate of 2 g/10 min (230 °C/2.16 kg). The PP-g-MA (OREVAC CA 100 of ARKEMA, Colombes Cedex, France) was used as compatibilizer for PET and PP. The maleic anhydrid content was 1 wt. %, and the melt flow rate was 10 g/10 min (190°C, 325 g). The sub-micron TiO₂ (Kronos 2220) with the average diameter of 300 nm was supplied by Kronos (Leverkusen, Germany).

Blending Procedures

Prior to processing, the PET was dried for 12 hours at 100 °C in order to avoid its hydrolytic degradation. The PP-g-MA was also dried for 12 hours at 80 °C. The PET/PP/TiO₂ (24.5/73.5/2 by volume) and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ (24.5/70.5/3/2) composites were prepared using the following four blending procedures.

Blending Procedure 1: the TiO₂ particles were blended with the PP in a Berstorff twin-screw extruder (ZE-25A UTX) firstly. The diameter of the screw was 25 mm and the L/D (length/diameter) was 44. The obtained PP/TiO₂ composite was subsequently blended with PET in with and without PP-g-MA in a Brabender twin-screw extruder (PL 2000) as the second step extrusion (diameter of the screw was 25 mm and L/D was 22). The extrusion temperatures from hopper to die were 230, 270, 275, 275 °C and the screw speed was 40 rpm. It should be pointed out that the PET was extruded in the Berstorff extruder before blending with the PP/TiO₂ composite.

Blending Procedure 2: the PP, PET and TiO₂ (or PP, PET, PP-g-MA and TiO₂) were fed into the Berstorff extruder simultaneously. The obtained composite was then extruded in the Brabender extruder for the second time, and the same extrusion parameters were used. The purpose was to subject this composite to same thermal mechanical history as the one prepared with blending Procedure 1.

Blending Procedure 3: the TiO₂ particles were firstly blended with PET in the Berstorff extruder. The obtained PET/TiO₂ composite was subsequently extruded with PP in absence (or presence) of PP-g-MA in the Brabender extruder.

Blending Procedure 4: the PET, PP and PP-g-MA were extruded with the Berstorff extruder as the first step extrusion. In the second step extrusion, the obtained PET/PP/PP-g-MA blend was blended with TiO₂ in the Brabender extruder.

After extrusion, the PET/PP/TiO₂ and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites were dried and injection molded into dog-bone specimens for tensile test. The injection molding temperatures from hopper to nozzle were 250, 275, 275, 275, 280 °C; the screw speed was 450 rpm. The designation of the composites prepared with the different blending procedures is given in Table 1. The components extruded in the first step extrusion are indicated within the brackets.

Table 1 Material composition and designation

Blending Procedure	Composition	Volume Ratio	Designation
1	PET/PP/TiO ₂	24.5/73.5/2	(PP/T)/PET
	PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO ₂	24.5/70.5/3/2	(PP/T)/PET/MA
2	PET/PP/TiO ₂	24.5/73.5/2	PP/PET/T
	PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO ₂	24.5/70.5/3/2	PP/PET/MA/T
3	PET/PP/TiO ₂	24.5/73.5/2	(PET/T)/PP
	PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO ₂	24.5/70.5/3/2	(PET/T)/PP/MA
4	PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO ₂	24.5/70.5/3/2	(PET/PP/MA)/T

Characterization

The extrudates were etched by xylene at 125 °C for 4 hours to remove PP. The etched extrudates and cryo-fractured surfaces of the extrudates were inspected by using scanning electron microscopes (JEOL JSM-6300 and ZEISS SupraTM 40VP) with an accelerating voltage of 25 kV. The fracture surfaces of the specimens were sputtered with Pd/Pt alloy before observation.

Disks of pure PET, PP, PET/TiO₂, PP/TiO₂ nanocomposites were pressed at 275 °C. The apparent viscosities of the PP and PP/TiO₂ were measured as a function of apparent shear rate evolved during extrusion at 275 °C using a Rheometrics ARES rheometer. All the rheological tests were performed in frequency mode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dispersion of TiO₂ Particles

SEM images in Figure 1a-d show the dispersion of TiO₂ in the PET/PP/TiO₂ and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites prepared with blending Procedures 1 and 2. Interestingly, for both blending procedures, without PP-g-MA the TiO₂ particles are exclusively located in the PET dispersed phase (Figure 1a and c), and in the PP matrix if

PP-g-MA is incorporated (Figure 1b and d). In case of blending Procedure 1 the extrusion was performed in two steps. Independent of the final composites, the TiO_2 particles are all located in the PP phase in the first extrusion step (PP/ TiO_2 composites); but after the second extrusion step (compounding the PP/ TiO_2 with PET), the particles are in the PET phase. For blending Procedure 1 this is not difficult to understand, as the PET/PP/ TiO_2 (or PET/PP/PP-g-MA/ TiO_2) composite is made by melt blending of the precompounded PP/ TiO_2 composite and PET (or PET together with PP-g-MA) during the second step extrusion. For blending Procedure 2, although all the components were fed simultaneously into the hopper, the PP incorporates the TiO_2 as it melts prior to the PET. Therefore blending procedure 1 and 2 are essentially the same. Based on this analysis it is believed that with both blending procedures, for the composites without PP-g-MA, the TiO_2 particles migrate from the PP to PET phase during extrusion. For the composites with PP-g-MA, this migration of TiO_2 does not take place, and all the particles stay in the PP. Therefore it is reasonable to conclude that the presence of PP-g-MA influences the preferential location of TiO_2 .

Figure 1. Dispersion of TiO₂ in PET/PP/TiO₂ and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites prepared with different blending procedures:

- (a) (PP/T)/PET and (b) (PP/T)/PET/MA prepared with blending Procedure 1,
 (c) PP/PET/T and (d) PP/PET/MA/T prepared with blending Procedure 2,
 (e) (PET/T)/PP and (f) (PET/T)/PP/MA prepared with blending Procedure 3,
 (g) (PET/PP/MA)/T prepared with blending Procedure 4.

The dispersion of TiO₂ particles in (PET/T)/PP and (PET/T)/PP/MA prepared according to blending Procedure 3 is shown in Figure 1e and f. Interestingly, for both composites the TiO₂ particles are dispersed in the PET phase. The presence of PP-g-MA does not influence the location of TiO₂. Figure 1g shows the dispersion of TiO₂ in the (PET/PP/MA)/T compounded by using blending Procedure 4. by which the TiO₂ particles are located on the surface of the PET droplets.

Influences of PP-g-MA and Blending Sequence on the Location of TiO₂

From the above observation, it is concluded that the location of TiO₂ particles is not only influenced by the incorporation of PP-g-MA, it is also affected by the blending sequence. The effects of PP-g-MA and blending sequence on the location of TiO₂ are summarized in Table 2. In absence of PP-g-MA, the TiO₂ are always dispersed in the PET phase irrespective of blending procedures. However, in presence of PP-g-MA, the location of TiO₂ is determined by blending sequence.

Table 2 Location of TiO₂ in the PET/PP/TiO₂ and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites prepared with different blending procedures

Blending Procedure	Location of TiO ₂	
	PET/PP/TiO ₂	PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO ₂
Blending Procedure 1	PET	PP
Blending Procedure 2	PET	PP
Blending Procedure 3	PET	PET
Blending Procedure 4	-	TiO ₂ layer on PET droplets

Inorganic fillers in polymer blends tend to interact more favorably with one particular phase, especially if the polarities of the two polymers are different. Therefore during melt blending usually migration of inorganic fillers takes place. It is widely accepted that the competitive interaction between inorganic fillers and polymers is the

thermodynamic driving force for the fillers' migration which results in their preferential location in one of the blend components. This competitive interaction can be predicted by Young's equation

$$\omega = \frac{\gamma_{N-A} - \gamma_{N-B}}{\gamma_{A-B}} \quad (1)$$

where the γ_{N-A} and γ_{N-B} are the interfacial tension between filler and polymer A, and the interfacial tension between filler and polymer B, respectively. If $\omega > 0$, that is, $\gamma_{N-A} > \gamma_{N-B}$, inorganic fillers are dispersed in polymer B or at the interface; if $\omega < 0$, that is, $\gamma_{N-A} < \gamma_{N-B}$, the fillers are in polymer A or at the interface [19].

Calculation of interfacial tension between inorganic fillers and polymer is given by the geometric-mean equation [22]:

$$\gamma_{N-A} = (\sqrt{\gamma_N^d} - \sqrt{\gamma_A^d})^2 + (\sqrt{\gamma_N^p} - \sqrt{\gamma_A^p})^2 \quad (2)$$

where the exponents d and p stand for the dispersive and polar contributions to the surface tension, respectively. At 270 °C (the extrusion temperature) γ_{PP} is much lower than γ_{PET} , and the values are listed in Table 3 [22]. The surface energy of the TiO₂ particles at 270 °C is unknown, but the inorganic fillers exhibit high surface energy values [23, 24]. For the composite without PP-g-MA, one can presume that $\gamma_{TiO_2-PP} > \gamma_{TiO_2-PET}$. Therefore it is not surprising that the TiO₂ particles are located in the PET.

Table 3. Surface tension of PET and PP at 270 °C

Material	Surface tension at 270 °C (mN/m)		
	γ	γ^d	γ^p
PET	28.3	22.0	6.3
PP	15.7	15.7	0

MA (maleic anhydride) is known to be an excellent ligand for metal oxides, it can be easily adsorbed onto the TiO₂ surface by electronic donation [25]. The number of OH groups of the TiO₂ particles depends on the crystal structure the TiO₂ as well as inter actions with visible light, UV-light respectively (Figure 2) [26]. But independent of those facts, the OH groups are always found at the TiO₂ surface which are able to react with the MA functional groups to build up the chemical bonds (as described in Figure 3). Breaking up of the anhydride structure of the PP-g-MA leads to carboxyl groups which are able to build up complex structure via acid-base inter actions, Homo/Lumo inter actions, respectively [27].

Figure 2. OH groups on the surface of TiO₂ particles

Figure 3. Interaction between the PP-g-MA and TiO_2

Those kind of interactions are in the case of PET more often which is a function of the degree of polarity as shown in Figure 4. This kind of acid-base interaction is so strong that in the (PP/T)/PET composite (blending Procedure 1) the TiO_2 particles migrate from the PP to the PET during the second extrusion step. Such kind of complexation and absorption are described in detailed in literatures [28, 29]. A reevaluation of the blending procedures reveals that during the preparation of (PP/T)/PET/MA (blending Procedure 1, Figure 1b) and PP/PET/MA/T (blending Procedure 2, Figure 1d), having a much lower melting temperature, the PP-g-MA melts before the PET although the two components are incorporated simultaneously. Therefore the PP-g-MA chains are absorbed onto the surface of TiO_2 particles. Surrounded by the PP chains the TiO_2 particles are compatible with the PP, and they stay in the PP instead of migrating to the PET phase.

Figure 4. Interaction between the PET and TiO_2

For the (PET/T)/PP/MA prepared with blending Procedure 3, the TiO_2 particles are precompounded with the PET. Consequently they are surrounded by the PET chains at the beginning of the second step extrusion. Therefore the incorporated PP-g-MA firstly reacts with the PET (via the maleic anhydride/PET terminal hydroxyl reaction) instead of interacting with the TiO_2 which is strongly absorbed by the PET phase. As a consequence, the TiO_2 particles remain in the PET phase. For blending Procedure 4, the PET, PP and PP-g-MA were fed simultaneously at the first step extrusion, the chemical

reaction between PP-g-MA and PET thereby takes place, resulting the accumulation of MA groups at the PET/PP interface. Favorably interacted with the MA, the incorporated TiO₂ particles are also located at the interface.

Phase morphology

As discussed earlier, blending Procedure 1 and 2 are essentially the same, therefore the investigation is focused on the composites prepared with blending Procedure 2 and 3. As shown in Figure 5, the PP/PET/T (blending Procedure 2) and (PET/T)/PP (blending Procedure 3) in which the TiO₂ particles are preferentially located in the PET show the similar morphology (Figure 5a and c). The PET droplets are large and exhibit wide size distribution ranging from 5 μm to 25 μm. In the PP/PET/MA/T (blending Procedure 2) the size of PET droplets are much smaller and the size distribution is narrower (Figure 5b). For the (PET/T)/PP/MA (blending Procedure 3), very fine PET droplets are observed in Figure 5d.

Figure 5. Morphology of PET/PP/TiO₂ and PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites prepared with blending Procedure 2 and 3.

- (a) PP/PET/T and (b) PP/PET/MA/T prepared with blending Procedure 2,
(c) (PET/T)/PP and (d) (PET/T)/PP/MA prepared with blending Procedure 3.

The incorporation of TiO₂ particles in one polymer phase will increase the viscosity of this phase. The viscosity curves for pure PET, PP and PET/TiO₂-8 vol.% and PP/TiO₂-3 vol.% composites are shown in Figure 6. It is evident that the viscosities of PET and PP are increased in presence of the TiO₂. However, although the PP contains only 3 vol.% of TiO₂ particles, its viscosity is greatly increased compared with the PET containing 8 vol.% of the TiO₂ particles. For PP/PET/T and (PET/T)/PP where the TiO₂ particles are exclusively located in PET, the deformability of PET droplets is abruptly reduced due to the increased viscosity, resulting large PET droplets [30]. While for PP/PET/MA/T the TiO₂ are dispersed in the PP, the increased viscosity of the PP enhances the breakup of PET droplets. A finer morphology is thereby observed (Figure 5b). For the PP/PET/MA/T and (PET/T)/PP/MA composites, the PP-g-MA acts as compatibilizer for the PET and PP phases. Although the viscosity of PET is increased by TiO₂, very fine phase morphology is still observed in the two composites because of the presence of PP-g-MA.

Figure 6. Viscosity of pure PP, PET, PP/TiO₂-3 vol.% and PET/TiO₂-8 vol.% composites at 275 °C as a function of the shear rate.

CONCLUSION

In the PET/PP/TiO₂ composites, the TiO₂ particles are always located in the PET phase irrespective of blending procedures. However, in PET/PP/PP-g-MA/TiO₂ composites the location of TiO₂ is depended on the blending sequence: blended with PP firstly or with PET and PP simultaneously (blending Procedure 1 and 2), the TiO₂ particles are dispersed in the PP phase; firstly blended with PET (blending Procedure 3), the TiO₂ particles stay in the PET; blended with the precompounded PET/PP/PP-g-MA, the TiO₂ particles are located on the surface of PET.

In absence of PP-g-MA the TiO₂ particles are driven into the thermodynamically preferred PET because of the interfacial difference ($\gamma_{\text{TiO}_2\text{-PET}}$ is lower than $\gamma_{\text{TiO}_2\text{-PP}}$). The MA of PP-g-MA is easily absorbed onto the TiO₂. Whether the interaction between TiO₂ and PP-g-MA can take place is governed the blending sequence. If the interaction takes place, covered by the PP chains the TiO₂ particles are compatible with PP, then the TiO₂ particles are dispersed in the PP phase.

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